

PREPARATION OF ARAMID/BN REINFORCED SELF-HEALABLE NANOCOMPOSITES AND THEIR PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Flexible electronics were easily suffering from mechanical damage in using process, with poor thermal conductivity in the insulation environment, which caused their functionalities lossing. Boron nitride nanosheets (BNNs) could enhance markedly composite materials' mechanical properties, electrical properties, thermal conductivity and moisture resistance. However, for certain applications in microelectronic field, materials that with higher mechanical properties and insulation properties are still needed. In order to further improving the mechanical strength and dielectric properties of BNNs reinforced self-healing nanocomposite material, aramid fiber will be introduced as another reinforcement into the system of nanocomposite via material mechanics performance analysis. Aramid fibers have excellent physical properties and mechanical properties. They could be transformed into the micro-fibers extremely easily, forming small size of the micro-fibers system. Adding them into the self-healing nanocomposite system is benefit to their dispersion. To further strengthen the compatibility and dispersity between aramid micro-fibers and BNNs, surface modification on aramid fiber is necessary to improve the surface roughness and activity. High-energy rays irradiation can penetrate into the sample deeply and do not need to consider the volume and shape of sample, which simplifying treatment process and avoiding the uneven modification of other modified methods.

In this paper, domestic aramid fibers were modified through "mutual irradiation grafting" at 200 kGy irradiating dose in the grafting liquid epoxy chloropropane, following the decorate treatment in dopamine. The obtained irradiated aramid micro-fibers (IAF) were used to reinforce the above BNNs self-healing nanocomposites. The mechanical strength, dielectric properties and self-heal ability of aramid/BNNs self-healable nanocomposite were studied and the results showed that organic aramid micro-fibers have a little influence on the dielectric constant and dielectric loss of nanocomposite, while the electric breakdown strength increased from 232.6 MV/m to 288.72 MV/m when the concentration of IAF was 10 wt%. Meanwhile, the tensile Young's modulus was improved obviously from 45.205 MPa to 56.796 MPa, with stable self-healing performance.

This work extends the application scope of self-healable supramolecular materials from conductive units to insulations and expands the material landscape available to flexible electronics and energy devices. We envision the integration of self-healing capability can significantly enhance functional materials longevity when they serve under harsh conditions such as frequent high voltage arcing, repeated mechanical distortions, and abrupt temperature changes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Inspired by biological systems where damage initiates an autonomous healing process, self-healing materials, which can repair the external or internal damages that they have sustained, have drawn a significant attention, due to the potential advantages they offer including greatly extended application lifetimes and reduced maintenance [1-5]. A variety of intense research approaches have emerged over the past decade to achieve this healable polymer materials [6], and they can be broadly classified as either autonomous self-healing systems, which include methods using encapsulated monomers that are released and polymerized upon material damage [7-10] or stimuli-responsive healable systems, such as thermally reversible covalent bond-forming moieties engineered into the polymer backbone [11-15]. Largely works focused on the designing unique stimulus-responsive polymer systems for the restoration of mechanical and structural properties recently. Besides, several functional materials, such as anti-fouling [16, 17], anti-corrosive [18], super hydrophobic [19] and electrically conductive materials [20-23] with self-healing properties have been successfully prepared. Among these materials, a typical supramolecular network system firstly reported by Leibler [24] has been chosen to be a kind of healable polymer matrix, which is further improved in mechanical strength, electrical conductivity and capacity by adding different fillers, such as μNi particles [23], grapheme oxide [25] and TiO_2 [20] etc. This system contains highly dynamic non-covalent bonds, showing a reversible “sticker-like” behavior enabling connection and reconnection between several hydrogen bonding regions [26]. Additionally, metal ion-polymer systems [27, 28], clay-dendrimer mixture [29], π - π stacking networks [13, 30, 31], Diels-Alder networks [32] and supra molecular hydrogels [33-35] have been also reported. In spite of the great promise these systems provide, there is one striking omission in their properties - a lack of high electrical resistivity and thermal conductivity in self-healing materials. This shortcoming limits their potential use in insulating application. Thus, further progress in fabrication of a repeatable self-healing material combining with excellent mechanical property and high resistivity remains a challenge.

In our previous study, a new self-healable dielectric nanocomposite was fabricated and reported, with high Young's modulus, good dielectric constant and loss, high breakdown strength [36]. Then the domestic aramid fiber, which was irradiated by high energy gamma-ray, was added into above nanocomposite system, as an organic reinforcement, to form an aramid/BNNSs self-healable nanocomposite system. The mechanical strength and dielectric properties of this new nanocomposite were studied and the results showed that organic aramid particles have a little influence on the dielectric constant and dielectric loss of composite, while the electric breakdown strength and the tensile Young's modulus were improved obviously.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Preparation of functional aramid micro-fiber

Domestic aramid fiber was chosen as the organic reinforcement. After cleaned in actone, aramid fibers were modified through “mutual irradiation grafting” at 200 kGy irradiating dose in the grafting liquid epoxy chloropropane, following the freezing broken to the micro-fiber. Then put above micro-fiber into 2 mg/ml dopamine solution in pH 8.0 Tris-HCl buffer solution and stir for 12 h in the air. Separate the solid product by centrifuge, clean, dry in the vacuum oven, and obtained the aiming organic reinforcement, irradiated aramid micro-fibers (IAF).

2.2 Preparation of aramid/BN reinforced self-healable nanocomposite

BN reinforced healable nanocomposites were fabricated according to our previous report, reference 36. 8% boron nitride nanosheets were added to the washed oligomer and refluxed at 130 °C for 1.5 h. Rise the temperature to 150 °C, add different quality functionalized aramid micro-fibers. After 3 h reaction, the black viscous product was obtained. Then placed it in Teflon mold, followed by pressing into 1 mm thickness nanocomposites, to be tested.

2.3 Characterization

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) measurements were performed with a Hitachi S-4800 field

emission electron microscope. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was conducted using Joel JEM-2010F. Mechanical tensile-stress and rheological experiments were carried out using Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) RSA G2 instrument. We tested four samples for each volume fraction. Tensile experiments were performed at room temperature (25°C) at a strain rate of 1mm/min. Dielectric constant and loss were measured using an Agilent LCR meter (E4980A). Dielectric breakdown strength measurements were performed on a TREK P0621P instrument using the electrostatic pulldown method under a DC voltage ramp of 500 Vs⁻¹. Self-healing tests of nanocomposite were performed by bringing several samples together and pressing with a compression pressure of ~350 kPa at 85 °C for 30 min. Optical images were recorded using Olympus BX51 optical microscope.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SEM and TEM

Microtopography of aramid micro-fibers and dopamine modified micro-fibers was observed by Scanning Electron Microscopy and Transmission electron microscopy, shown as Figure 1.

Figure 1: SEM images of a) aramid micro-fibers and b) dopamine modified micro-fibers, c) TEM images of dopamine-modified micro-fibers

In Figure 1, it can be clearly seen the interface combination status between aramid micro-fiber and dopamine nano film. The dark aramid fiber was surrounded tightly by light-colored poly dopamine nano layer, with uniform nano layer thickness.

3.2 Young's Modulus of nanocomposite

Aramid with the high crystallinity, could improve the mechanical strength of the composites when it was used as an organic reinforcement. Especially after the surface modification, the reactive functional groups on its surface could be more closely combined with polymer matrix, which contribute to the enhancement of composite materials' overall performance. Figure 2 shows the tensile Young's modulus of nanocomposites with different content of aramid microfibers and then make the contrast to the original pristine polymer.

Figure 2: Young's modulus of aramid reinforced nanocomposites with different aramid concentration

It can be seen from Figure 2 that the Young's modulus of the composites increases with the content of aramid fiber in the nanocomposites. When the content of the aramid fiber reaches 10 wt. %, Young's modulus went up to 56.796 MPa. The mechanical properties of the composites were significantly higher than those of the pristine polymer prepared by Leibler method (1.519 MPa), indicating that the compatibility between the high toughness organic microfibers and the high stiffness inorganic boron nitride nanosheets is better. It is the synergistic effect of the two reinforcements that promoted the mechanical strength of the composites

3.3 Dielectric property

Figure 3 shows the dielectric constant and dielectric loss of aramid fiber composite with different aramid micro-fiber content. The self-healing properties of nanocomposites containing 10 wt.% aramid microfibers were tested.

Figure 3: Dielectric constant and loss of aramid reinforced nanocomposites. a) nanocomposites with different aramid concentration, b) 10 wt.% aramid nanocomposites vs. healing cycles at 1000 Hz

The influence of the introduction of aramid microfibers on the dielectric constant and dielectric loss of the composites is not obvious. When the frequency is 1000 Hz, the dielectric constant of the composite is basically stable between 3.8 and 4, and the dielectric loss is 0.17~0.18, indicating that the intrinsic dielectric constant and loss of aramid fiber is slightly higher than that of boron nitride nanosheets. After repeated self-repair process, the dielectric properties of the composite material are basically maintained in the original state, as shown in Figure 3, indicating that the dielectric properties of the material have been repaired.

3.4 Breakdown strength

Figure 4 shows the results of the electrical breakdown strength test with 10 wt.% aramid fiber composite, and the change of the breakdown strength of the material after three healing cycles is investigated.

The introduction of aramid dramatically improves the electrical breakdown strength of the composites. After three the repair process, the material's breakdown strength is basically maintained at 276.71 ± 17.24 MV/m, which realizes the self-repairing of the high pressure resistance of self-healable nanocomposite.

Figure 4: Breakdown strength of IAMF3-DPA reinforced nanocomposites vs. healing cycles

3.5 Self-healable property

Figure 5 shows the optical images of aramid/BNNs nanocomposite fracture section before and after healing process.

Figure 5: Optical image of aramid/BNNs nanocomposite fracture section a) before and b) after healing process

It can be seen that through cut, contact and pressurized heating process, the crack of the cross section has basically disappeared. The dopamine-modified surface of aramid microfibers carries a large amount of hydroxyl and amino groups. On the one hand, the structure of these active groups is similar to the molecular structure of the polymer matrix so that they can bind to each other with good wettability. On the other hand, the N-H bond and the H-O bond from the functionalized aramid microfibers can interact with the polymer matrix and the amidated boron nitride nanobelts in the form of hydrogen bonds. Under the joint action of these three hydrogen bonds, the nanocomposites maintain the original self-healing performance. When the material is broken into two parts and then contact with each other, the amide active groups from the polymer matrix, BNNs and aramid fiber in the cross-section, can be combined as the role of hydrogen bonds, to reform the joint structure and achieve self-repair process.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Aramid micro-fiber was functionalized by dopamine, and then was adapted to the compatibility of self-repairing polymer system to enhance the nanocomposite properties as an organic reinforcement. By analysing the mechanical properties, dielectric properties and self-repair properties of aramid-doped and boron nitride-reinforced nanocomposites, it was found that the tensile Young's modulus of nanocomposite was increased from 45.205 MPa to 56.796 MPa with 10 wt.% aramid, compared to the composites without the addition of aramid micro fibers. The dielectric constant and dielectric loss of

the composites did not change significantly. The dielectric constant was stable between 3.8 and 4 and the dielectric loss is in the range of 0.17~0.18. The electric breakdown strength was increased from 232.6 MV/m to 288.72 MV/m.

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